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THE CONCEPT, ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF STRATEGIC AUDIT AT THE PRESENT STAGE OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The article is devoted to such a modern direction of development of auditing activities in Russia as strategic audit. Currently, requests for audit results have a fairly strong impact on the overall approach to the organization of audit activities and audit methodology, which gave rise to such a concept as "strategic audit".

Keywords: strategic audit, audit activity, audit.

The development of international cooperation, the strengthening of integration processes that took place at the beginning of the XXI century put forward new requirements for the methods of managing the company, in terms of developing an effective development strategy. Currently, the concept of strategic planning allows you to anticipate trends in the development of the company's business and timely determine adequate changes in business. In the conditions of the economic crisis caused by the pandemic, as well as the introduction of economic sanctions, the organization's development strategy should have such a quality as complexity, be focused on the long term and significantly influence the forms of interaction between business and society and government agencies in the interests of joint development of partners.

In this regard, a significant number of enterprises began to pay serious attention to issues of marketing analysis, logistics, improvement of structures based on the development of cooperation with other organizations, the formation of business networks, as well as issues of control (audit) of the chosen development strategy, which created the prerequisites for the emergence of a strategic audit.

Strategic audit involves conducting an audit of various types of organizational strategies in order to establish their validity, reality, achievability and effectiveness.

The need for strategic management is dictated by the following inherent factors in the business environment:

- the emergence of new requests and a change in the position of the consumer;
- increasing competition for resources;
- internationalization of business;
- development of information networks that allow to disseminate and receive information at a high speed;

- wide availability of modern technologies;
- changing the role of human resources.

According to Trigub E. Yu. "The main feature of strategic audit, in contrast to the generally accepted audit of financial statements, is that it refers to future information about the activities of the organization and its business environment. Strategic audit is a kind of direction of the traditional audit of financial statements towards the audit of the near future, i.e. business audit" [1, p. 123].

In modern economic literature, based on the importance of strategic audit, much attention is paid to the directions of its development. However, there is no consensus on the definition of the essence and content of the strategic audit yet.

Some authors define strategic audit as a type of management audit that examines the prospects of the corporation as a whole and provides a comprehensive assessment of the corporate situation. Other authors expand the concept of strategic audit.

The founder of the scientific concept of marketing, F. Kotler, saw strategic audit as one of the main tools for collecting important information, including information used in the development of specific business goals and strategies [2].

Thompson A.A. and Strickland A.J. under strategic audit understand the degree of policy coherence with strategic resources, strategic and external climate and positions of the enterprise [3, p. 178].

American economist I. Ansoff understood strategic audit to mean a certain degree of policy coherence with strategic resources, the external climate and the positions of the enterprise [4, p. 113].

Among Russian economists, interesting points of view on the concept of strategic audit are expressed by teachers of the Rostov State University of Economics

Bogataya I.N., Alekseeva I.V., Emelyanova I.N., Khakhonova N.N.

Thus, I.N. Bogataya, taking into account the influence of external and internal factors on the strategy of an economic entity, defines strategic audit as an auditor's study of the strategic conditions in which a commercial organization operates, as well as an audit of a business idea and its subsequent implementation. The audit involves conducting a strategic analysis, evaluating the strategic choice made and the implementation of the chosen strategy [5, p. 89].

Alekseeva I.V. understands strategic audit as an assessment of the adequacy of the accounting system based on financial, tax and management audit data, focused on the long term, taking into account the influence of external factors of the macro environment [6, p. 116].

According to I.N. Yemelyanova, strategic audit is "a special technique that allows you to assess the resource availability and feasibility of the stated plans, covering the collection, verification and analysis of reliable strategic (forecast) information, including information generated by accounting and non-accounting systems of companies" [7, p. 89].

There is also a point of view according to which a strategic audit is a service accompanying the audit and is carried out in order to establish the reliability, realism and possibility of using forward-looking information, as well as the correctness of its preparation based on accepted assumptions and the adequacy of its presentation [8, p. 149; 9, p.134].

Currently, there are no international standards, as well as federal regulatory legal acts regulating and determining the need for a strategic audit. Each audit organization independently determines the forms, types and procedure for conducting a strategic audit, as well as evaluating its effectiveness, taking into account the specifics of the organization's structure. Insufficient formalization of the strategic audit process, the absence of internal corporate standards and regulations do not allow purposefully solving organizational and methodological issues of the implementation of this audit service in the business environment.

Confirmation of the importance of strategic audit for the modern economy of Russia is, in our opinion, the development and approval by the Accounts Chamber of Russia of the Standard of External State Audit (control) SGA 105 "Strategic Audit" (approved by the resolution of the Board of the Accounts Chamber of the Russian Federation dated November 10, 2020 No. 17PC), which entered into force: November 10, 2020. The developer of this standard is the Department of Research and Methodology of the Accounting Chamber of the Russian Federation [10].

According to the results of the strategic audit, it is necessary to:

- find out the validity of the organization's strategy;
- assess the adequacy of the organizational structure and corporate governance system to strategic goals;
- develop corrective measures to change the adopted strategy based on trends in the development of the external and internal environment.

The auditor should recommend to the management the necessary actions to adapt its strategy to the conditions of transformation. At the same time, it is important to focus all the activities of the organization on strategy and apply end-to-end planning, in which the strategy should be reflected in the functional plans of departments and individual responsibility centers.

We fully share the position of V.G. Shirobokov that: "Strategic audit should be an integral element of strategic management. Companies need to integrate this process into the management system so that it responds in a timely and adequate manner to changes in external or internal events" [11, p. 63]. The ability to adapt its activities in a timely manner to changes in external and internal factors is one of the key abilities of an organization to ensure its long-term economic success and achieve strategic goals.

All of the above determines the relevance of the development of the methodology of strategic audit in audit organizations, the evaluation of its effectiveness and the development of internal standards governing its implementation.

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